

HOME READING FOR UNIVERSITY EFL STUDENTS: ITS IMPACT AND THE PERSPECTIVES OF TEACHERS AND STUDENTS

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Abstract: *Research on second language acquisition continues to center on the impact of reading on general communicative ability. In instance, reading a lot gives students rich input and aids in language acquisition. Extensive reading (ER) has been found to be beneficial by research; nonetheless, there is currently little data demonstrating the connection between ER and general competence, and writing competence in particular. The current study looked into how teachers' and students' opinions on the use of ER related to overall English language proficiency. 40 Uzbek university students took part in the activity. Along with questionnaire answers and interview transcripts, the data also includes results from pre- and post-tests that gauge pupils' abilities in reading, writing, and listening. The study's conclusions suggest that there is some evidence to support the usefulness of ER for the student participants, which has consequences for English instruction and learning in EFL settings.*

Key words: *language testing, learner attitudes, learner perceptions, reading, EFL teaching and learning.*

I. Introduction

Most language learners experience a range of emotions during the process of learning a second language, including excitement, uncertainty, irritation, and others. Some people may feel helpless and suffer from this emotion, or they may give up on learning the language entirely. Fortunately, many people have mastered the challenges of language acquisition and demonstrated confidence in utilizing it. Those working in the field of language education have been particularly interested in factors that facilitate language acquisition and reduce learner anxiety.

The research findings reinforce the argument for ER's inclusion in language learning and instruction. Schema theory, for instance, explains how readers might interpret text. Its main argument is that a text cannot convey meaning on its own. The reader introduces the «schemata» to the text. Consider the reader understanding of the

world, culture, feelings, past experiences, and other things that aid in the reader's interpretation of the written text can all schemata. As a result, reading becomes easier when books include language and material that appeal to the reader's interests or relate to what they already know.

B. Literature Review

Numerous studies have been carried out to look into the connection between fluency in language and substantial reading. Lee, Krashen, and Gribbons as one's success described language ability on exams assessing one's proficiency with restricted relative clauses. Significantly, it was discovered that the only factor that could accurately predict exam performance was a lot of reading. In a 20-week period, Leung's case study examined the connection between reading a lot and an adult's self-study. The practice of extensive reading has been found to have an impact on vocabulary and reading ability.

Results from the pre- and post-tests demonstrated that students' reading and vocabulary improved more when they read more self-selected books. There are many research on the impact of ER on language learning. Although a considerable number of studies (e.g., Lightbown 2002; Shih, 2015; Williams, 2007) were unable to provide meaningful results, several had findings indicating the beneficial impact of ER on linguistic competency. For instance, Shih looked at how much reading college students did and discovered that while reading a lot did not enhance reading competency, the experimental group did see an improvement in their usage of reading techniques. Additionally, Williams used a time-lapse methodology to study the impact of ER programs on elementary school pupils and discovered that four years after the testing results, the retesting results were lower. Studies have also highlighted the challenges associated with its implementation and the reasons behind its failure. However, ER has a general favorable impact on reading competence, all language skills, vocabulary sizes, reading rate improvements, and the application of reading techniques, according to the majority of research on the subject.

Methodology

The current study used a mixed research design that comprised a qualitative research method and the pre- and post-test method. Prior to and following the two-semester deployment of heavy reading, participants in this study were invited to take writing and listening assessments, both designed by teacher. In the meantime, they were requested to complete a questionnaire assessing their opinions and views regarding the substantial reading practice that was necessary for all second-year English majors, in addition to taking the pretests and posttests. (See Table 1 for the

research’s quantitative section’s design). At the conclusion of the first semester, tape recordings of the instructor interviews were made.

Test	Pretest		Posttest		Gain	Student’s view
	Mean	StD	Mean	StD		
Listening						
Reading						
Writing						
Attitude	Pretest		Posttest			

Table 1. Research design for quantitative part

Students Involved

The study’s subjects were 40 second-year English majors. They were basically at the low to high intermediate levels of English proficiency.

The Teacher’s Participation in the Reading Program

Students had to study independently assessed English novels or works on Modern literature that were specifically purchased and reserved in the university library for English majors for sophomore reading classes. Ideally, students would complete various types of writing (such keeping a reading log) or write a report about the book they read, depending on what their teachers asked of them.

Data Analysis

Statistical techniques were used to analyze the pretest and posttest data gathered by the usage of the writing test and the questionnaire. The transcript of the interview was done verbatim. A verbatim record of the interview data is necessary for the investigator to feel confidence about their results.

Results

All participants recorded their voices on a book moral and briefly retold the plot. By observing their understanding of the book plot, it was oblivious every student managed to work out new knowledge by reading novels in short time. It was stated that many students were motivated to check out the books that their friends had recommended as a result of this ER implementation. Most students feel they are motivated to borrow books through ER, especially those with very positive comments from their peers. Reading became more apparent to them than it had previously. While some with weak reading comprehension believed they could read more quickly, others requested to read more. There are comparatively more students who consider their English ability to be poor feel they can read faster now.

In their upcoming reading lessons, adjustments would be made. Satisfaction with the implementation of ER and its results, but how to enhance reading instruction for

new pupils in the upcoming academic year beyond adhering to the most basic type of ER implementation. Because of their aptitude for putting new ideas into practice and interest in ER-related research teaching, they had a comparatively strong desire to improve their ER promotion. We suggested increasing the percentage of ER in the specific course grade for instructor.

Conclusion

The study's findings have implications for language learning and instruction as well as partial support for ER in terms of its impact on learning outcomes, student attitudes toward it, and instructor perception.

Rich in insights into language teaching and learning as well as research pertaining to extensive reading, the results of this study on extensive reading and its relationship with English language learning and affective aspects are presented. This study found a positive correlation between students' growth in writing proficiency and the quantity of books they read. This information can be used to confidently advocate ER to a larger demographic. In the event that an alternative relationship is found, ER care should be started. The answers from the teacher and student participants also provided details that direct the practice of extended reading.

This study has also advanced the field's understanding of the relationship between extensive reading and language proficiency, particularly in the area of writing. Its unique research design, which combines quantitative and qualitative methods for data collection and analysis, and its use of English majors as subjects set it apart from previous studies. Future research must address the limitations of this study, even though the number of books each student read had an impact on their writing tests, the pre- and post-test designs also demonstrated an increase in their English ability reflected on their test scores, and students' questionnaire responses exhibited a perceived positive effect on their English learning. Its failure to use a comparison research strategy, which contrasts the outcomes of participant groups receiving various treatments, is one of its limitations. Subsequent investigations into the extensive reading habits of university students in analogous settings could employ a quasi-experimental design to furnish additional proof of the correlation between extensive reading and English proficiency. **This study's additional restriction** stems from the fact that its participants were first-year English majors who were exposed to various English learning approaches. In order to reduce the exposure non-majors may receive during the research time, future studies should think about sampling them.

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